

Implementation and Testing of a Soft Computing based Model Predictive Control on an Industrial Controller

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Abstract

This work presents a real time testing approach of an Intelligent Multiobjective Nonlinear-Model Predictive Control Strategy (iMO-NMPC). The main goal is the testing and analysis of the feasibility and reliability of some Soft Computing (SC) techniques running on a real time industrial controller. In this predictive control strategy, a Multiobjective Genetic Algorithm is used together with a Recurrent Artificial Neural Network in order to obtain the control action at each sampling time. The entire development process, from the numeric simulation of the control scheme to its implementation and testing on a PC-based industrial controller, is also presented in this paper. The computational time requirements are discussed as well. The obtained results show that the SC techniques can be also considered to tackle highly nonlinear and coupled complex control problems in real time, thus optimising and enhancing the response of the control loop. Therefore this work is a contribution to spread the SC techniques in on-line control applications, where currently they are relegated mainly to be used off-line, as is the case of optimal tuning of control strategies.

Keywords: Multiobjective Genetic Algorithm, Neural Network, NMPC, HiL Testing, Industrial Controller

1. Introduction

The study and design of efficient, optimised and accurate control strategies for complex plants or systems in the Industry is a remaining challenge. The characterisation of real plants includes complex features such as highly nonlinear and coupled dynamics, several competing objectives, chaotic disturbances, randomness and uncertainties among others ([1], [2]). These features increase the complexity of the design of control systems (especially when the plant also must work in different and continuously variable operating points), making it difficult to obtain satisfactory results when the control problem is addressed through classical control theories and hard computing techniques.

As Rudas and Fodor described in their work [3], Intelligent Systems (IS) provide a standardized methodological approach to solve important and fairly complex problems obtaining consistent and reliable results over time. In Computational Sciences the intelligence of a system can be characterised by its flexibility, adaptability, capacity for learning, reasoning, dealing with complex dynamics, as well as its capacity for managing uncertain and imprecise information. An overview of the IS and the different approaches based on intelligence is provided in [3]. The Computational Intelligence ([4], [5]), the SC ([6], [7], [8]) and the Hybrid Systems ([9], [10]) are examples of such approaches. In the last years, techniques coming from these paradigms have provided opportunities in engineering design, control and research in industrial applications, as it is pointed out in [11].

Nowadays it is possible to find control applications and research works addressed using IS, offering advanced solutions for many complex industrial control problems. Some of these solutions are based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), such as in [12] where an introduction and perspective of using ANN in motor drives control is given, or in [13] where a new approach of a brain-emotional-learning-based intelligent controller is studied. Another widely spread technique in industrial applications is the Fuzzy Logic (FL) where some of the latest applications are listed in a recent review [14].

In the searching process context of a complex nonlinear multiobjective optimisation problem, it is possible to select different methods to obtain the set of non-inferior (Pareto) solutions. Nowadays, methods based on evolutionary

algorithms (EA) are probably the most popular alternative, being the high computational cost their main drawback, especially when fast convergence time and real time characteristics are required. Several works dealing with this task can be found in ([15], [16], [17]). Efficient EAs such as Nondominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA), Micro-Genetic Algorithm, and Adaptive Genetic Algorithm are contributions presented in [18], [19], and [20] respectively. Other relevant drawbacks appear when system stability and robustness analysis are pursued. The analysis of these aspects implies a very high complexity due to the requirement of a convergence analysis of the heuristic searching methods.

In recent years the Evolutionary Computing (where GAs are included) is progressively being introduced into industrial process control applications [1]. Most of the works in this area are related to project scheduling of industrial processes ([21], [22]), or to obtain an optimised set-up or configuration of the processes which can include the calculation of the control systems' parameters ([23], [16], [24], [25]). Nevertheless there is a relatively low number of GAs as the core of real time control strategies. A recent approach in which a Multiobjective Genetic Algorithm is the core component of a hybrid predictive control strategy can be found in [26]. Most of this kind of studies have shown promising results over highly complex dynamic systems in numerical simulation frameworks.

The lack of real time implementation, analysis and validation of previously mentioned developments for their introduction in real industrial processes is an important drawback. This could be addressed by pursuing more realistic simulation frameworks (with a better approach to the real control systems). The problem is the development and testing laboratory equipment, which usually differs from the industrial equipment such as the PC-based industrial computers (PCIC), real time embedded systems, programmable logic controllers or programmable automation controllers (PAC). Furthermore, real conditions such as uncertainties, noisy or imprecise measurements, disturbances and complex nonlinear dynamics, among others, are usually not considered in the early simulation stages.

The work presented in [27] provided the first steps towards the implementation of a SC based control strategy in real industrial controllers such a PCIC and a PAC. The early real time implementation of a GA as a core of a Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) strategy showed the real capabilities of some real time industrial platforms to cope with such complex control problems. In this first approach a single objective control strategy was implemented and characterised in two hardware platforms, despite the adapted Nondominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) being a multiobjective GA. The main goal of the work was the evaluation of the computational cost, including the analysis of the computational time requirements for such kind of hardware controllers running the GA-based single objective predictive control strategy. Therefore, a Hardware in the Loop (HiL) setup and the testing of simple control strategy based on a GA were the most important topics addressed in [27].

The motivation of the present work is to take a step further towards the implementation of the SC techniques on real industrial hardware. For this purpose, the single objective predictive control strategy presented in [27] has been improved to address multiobjective problems, leading to a more realistic multiobjective predictive control scenario. The second enhancement to the previous work [27] is related to the type of model used in the NMPC strategy. The mathematical model of the system to be controlled has been replaced by an ANN model, thus providing greater versatility to the control scheme. Through this work the different implementation steps are presented, as well as the results obtained in each one.

The paper is organised as follows: The multiobjective GA approach used in the multiobjective NMPC strategy is presented in section 2. Section 2.1 describes the improvements introduced in the controller and the control strategy in comparison to the previous work [27]. The hardware platforms and the plants models to be controlled are introduced in section 3. Results of the control strategy both in simulation and HiL testing approach are presented in section 4. The capabilities of the hardware to execute the control algorithm and the computational time requirements are analysed and discussed in section 4.3. Finally, the conclusions and future actions are shown in section 5.

2. NSGA-II as optimisation solver in NMPC schemes

When dealing with real complex control problems, some of the control objectives are competing simultaneously and the improvement of one of them can negatively affect some of the others. When optimal control issues are pursued (as in the case of NMPC), such problems are solved by searching for the set of non-inferior solutions, also known as the set of Pareto solutions [28]. In order to find those solutions the NMPC scheme performs predictions of the control loop evolution over a predictive horizon (using a model) basing on the possible control actions. An optimisation

Figure 1: Pareto front solutions and Decision Making selection vs samples

problem is formulated for the defined horizon in order to obtain the control actions that produce the best performance (usually evaluating a single cost function with aggregated objectives) of the control loop. This procedure is repeated at each control sampling time using a receding horizon. When multiple and non-aggregated objectives are handled, a multiobjective optimisation problem must be solved at each control sampling time. This is illustrated by the NMPC simulation example shown in figure 1, where it is possible to see how different Pareto sets can be obtained depending on the control problem state (transient, steady state, etc.). In this example, the competing objectives to be minimised are the error of the controlled variable and the increment of the control action (smooth control actions are desired). In the figure, the control set point is shown in a continuous line (step). It can be observed how the Pareto sets of solutions significantly expands in the transient response when the selected objectives are competing simultaneously. Another aspect to be noticed in the figure is the fact that the Pareto fronts appear 4 samples before the step reference due to the receding horizon selected for the multiobjective NMPC strategy (four samples for this simulation example).

When a proper convergence of the searching algorithm is accomplished all the solutions in the Pareto set can be considered as 'optimal' in a multiobjective context, so a decision making algorithm must be used in order to select a solution among the Pareto set according to some criterion. This solution will be finally the control action at each control sampling time. Different criteria can be adopted in the decision making algorithm. A criterion based on the selection of the solution with the minimum distance to the origin of the Pareto graph was adopted in [29]. Additionally the decision making algorithm could adopt an expert criterion based on a Fuzzy Inference System as can be found in [26].

In the present work, the NSGA-II proposed by Deb et al. in [30] has been used and implemented in real time as the optimisation solver in the multiobjective NMPC scheme. This algorithm is an improvement of the previous NSGA proposed by Srinivas and Deb in [18] emerging to overcome the main criticisms that NSGA received [30], i.e. the lack of elitism, the poor specification of sharing parameters and the high computational complexity. Using a fast nondominated sorting approach with $O(MN^2)$ computational complexity (being M the number of objectives and N the population size) and due to its elitist mechanisms, the convergence time of the Pareto front was improved. Moreover, a much better spread of solutions is achieved as was demonstrated in [30]. Both characteristics, i.e. its fast convergence and its very good and intrinsically obtained (with no parameter adjusting) spread of solutions, were the main reasons to choose this algorithm [26]. The working of NSGA-II is described in more detail in [30].

In this work, the NMPC control of two single-input single-output (SISO) nonlinear systems used as benchmark has been implemented and tested. In both cases, two control objectives (competing in the control problem) have been defined. It should be noticed that the scope of this work is an improvement and a continuation of the previous work presented in [27] where a framework for the rapid prototyping and testing of intelligent control techniques on industrial control platforms was presented.

2.1. Improvements in the NSGA-II based NMPC control

In [27] some simplifications and assumptions were made in the NMPC controller in order to obtain the first test results on the HiL testing setup. Those tests required the rewriting of the NSGA-II code provided by Deb et. al. in [30] in order to be developed in the Matlab®/Simulink® rapid prototyping environment, to adapt it to be executed in real time, and to add a new stopping criterion involving the control loop execution time for working in a deterministic way.

The present work carries out some improvements enabling to exploit the full capacity of the NSGA-II to handle multiobjective optimisation problems. As it was mentioned before, two competing objectives have been defined in the control strategy. The first objective (eq.1) is related to the minimisation of the control loop tracking error $e(k)$ (system output error with respect to the desired set-point) typically used in control engineering. In eq.1, H is the receding horizon of the NMPC strategy, and k the actual sampling (step) time in the control loop. The second control objective (eq.2) evaluates the variation of the control action $u(k)$ and its main purpose is to reduce sudden changes in the control action, aiming to obtain a smooth response.

$$ob1 = \sum_{h=k}^{k+H} (y(h) - ref(h))^2 \quad (1) \quad ob2 = \sum_{h=k}^{k+H} (u(h) - u(h-1))^2 \quad (2)$$

Accordingly the NSGA-II tries to provide the Pareto set of optimal solutions at each control sampling time. The quality and spread of this Pareto set is highly dependent on the time available for solving the optimisation problem (one sampling time in NMPC) and on the time required for the NSGA-II to converge (which in turn depends on the problem size and tuning of the algorithm). If a good convergence behaviour is ensured all the solutions in the Pareto set can be a control action candidate for that sampling time. To deal with the final control action selection a decision making algorithm has been implemented based on a balanced minimum distance criterion [29].

On the other hand, the NMPC needs a plant model approach to perform the predictions of the control loop over the selected horizon. This prediction is used to evaluate and rank (in terms of the control objectives) of the possible candidates (control action solutions) proposed by the NSGA-II at each generation. Different techniques exist for this model approach, such as the knowledge based mathematical models, FL or ANN modelling techniques, among others. In this work, an approach based on ANNs has been selected because of their capabilities to approximate black-box nonlinear systems based on experimental input-output data. Therefore a more realistic scenario (in which the mathematical model of the plant to be controlled is not known) can be adopted. Moreover, as the ANN can be trained off-line, it did not imply a relevant difference in the computational cost comparing to the mathematical model, especially when compared to the cost of the NSGA-II.

3. Testing setup description

It is well known that testing executed via numerical simulations can provide accurate results for the analysis and understanding of the entire control loop. However, these simulations do not always give enough information to understand and represent the real behaviour of the controlled variables. Often, once the simulation stage is finished, the tests are extended to real systems. This step has the risk of unexpected behaviours that simulations do not show, which sometimes is simply unacceptable (e.g. due to cost or safety reasons). The HiL testing approach arises as an intermediate step between software simulations and real testing, providing the developer with a key tool to test the entire process as well as just small pieces of code [31]. HiL setups have been tested successfully in many different industrial applications such as automotive solutions [15], wind energy systems [32] or electronics [17].

As shown in figure 2, the HiL setup consists of an PC-based modular Industrial controller (host) where the control strategy is embedded. This is connected to a generic PC target in which the controlled plant model is simulated. The developer externally wires and connects the input and output signals of both systems. The Industrial PC is a very robust hardware platform, with an Intel® Pentium® M clocked at 1.8 GHz and using RTAI as operating system (OS). The RTAI OS stands for Real Time Application Interface for Linux, being one of the most successful open source real time OS. The industrial controller has a PCI industrial bus that holds a National Instruments™ analog IO card (PXI-6052). The target is a generic PC (running the xPC-Target 4.0 real time embedded OS from MathWorks®) in

Figure 2: Matlab[®]/Simulink[®] Block diagram

which a National Instruments[™] PCI Data Acquisition card (PCI-6281) is used as input and output module. The figure 2 shows the Simulink[®] block diagram with both the host and the target elements.

Two nonlinear benchmark models have been selected to be used as systems to be controlled. As described before, these models are embedded into the xPC based real time target.

System 1 (A modified version of the system presented in [33] to increase the nonlinear dynamics near the origin.)

$$y_{k+1} = 0.8 \left[u_k^3 + \frac{y_k \cdot y_{k-1}}{1 + y_k^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

System 2 (Extracted from [34])

$$y_{k+1} = \frac{1.5 \cdot y_k \cdot y_{y-1}}{1 + y_k^2 + y_{k-1}^2} + 0.7 \sin [0.5 (y_k + y_{k-1})] \cos [0.5 (y_k + y_{k-1})] + 1.2u_k \quad (4)$$

For each nonlinear plant model approach a Recurrent MultiLayer Perceptron ANN has been selected. For the system 1 (eq.3) the ANN has a 3-6-1 topology. The system 2 (eq.4) has been modelled by a 3-3-1 topology ANN. In both networks the output signal is fed back into two of the inputs. They have a sigmoid activation function on the hidden layer and a linear function on the output layer. These ANNs have been trained from several input-output data obtained experimentally by using the already known mathematical model of the plant (equations 3 & 4). It should be noticed that a chirp signal input was used in order to excite and capture the nonlinearities and high dynamic responses of the plants, thus obtaining a richer model approach. The well-known Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm has been selected for the training of the ANNs.

In figure 3 the mathematical plant model and the ANN estimated responses are displayed in the same graph. The results are satisfactory although in this particular example the ANN model presents a small offset-error in the stationary response (gain error). The modelling error (always present in real control problems) can affect the NMPC control loop response as can be seen in the figures 5 & 7 in the forthcoming section 4. Some feedback corrections could be implemented in order to reduce or compensate the error in the NMPC control loop in order to increase its robustness.

The implemented NSGA-II parameter settings are the following: 4 real variables for each individual (corresponding to a horizon of 4 samples $[u(k+1), u(k+2), \dots, u(k+H)]$), 2 objective functions (see eq.1 & eq.2), a population size of 70 individuals, a maximum number of 100 generations, a cross-over probability of 60%, a mutation probability of 10% and a random seed of 50%. The searching algorithm is stopped when 100 generations are executed or when the sampling period window is about to be reached.

Figure 3: System identification results a) System 1 and b) System 2

4. Results

The testing and validation of the whole control system has been done with numerical (sec.4.1) and real time HiL simulation (sec.4.2) approaches. 200 experiments have been performed, 100 with each of both approaches, of which 50 correspond to the NMPC+mathematical model and the other 50 correspond to the NMPC+ANN model. In all the cases the reference defined for the controlled variable (y_k) in system 1 was a step of amplitude 0.3 whereas the reference for the system 2 was a step of amplitude 1. The control sampling time, T_s , was set to $0.2s$ for both systems. The control objectives have been defined previously in this paper (section: 2.1).

The tables show statistics and representative values over 50 simulations, such as the max. overshoot (M_{p_Max}), the min. overshoot (M_{p_Min}), the mean value of the overshoot (M_{p_Mean}), the variance of the overshoot ($M_{p_Variance}$), the max. variation of $u(k)$ ($Max \Delta u(k)$), and the steady state error percentage (e_{ss}). It is important to note that the systems' responses variation between simulations was extremely low (variance value in the order of 10^{-5} and mode value around 10^{-3}) which can give an idea of the NSGA-II convergence property and the robustness of the proposed control solution.

4.1. Numerical Simulation

In this section, the results obtained by numerical simulation using both plant model approaches, i.e., the mathematical and the ANN model approaches, are shown. The table 1 show the results for the numerical simulations.

		M_{p_Max}	M_{p_Min}	M_{p_Mean}	$M_{p_Variance}$	$Max \Delta u(k)$	e_{ss}
Math Model	System 1	0.35	0.33	0.34	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.29	3%
	System 2	1.46	1.30	1.38	$1.032 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.70	3%
ANN Model	System 1	0.39	0.37	0.38	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.32	7%
	System 2	1.50	1.29	1.38	$1.662 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.43	3%

Table 1: Simulation using the mathematical and the ANN model approach

4.1.1. Simulation using the mathematical model approach

The figures 4(a) and 4(b) show the systems' responses. The results prove that both systems can be controlled with the NSGA-II based multiobjective NMPC controller. In comparison to the results obtained in [27] for the same systems under the same testing conditions, the multiobjective version of the controller shows a better response (smoother control). This can be seen in the maximum variation of the control action $u(k)$ which has been drastically reduced (objective 2). Without going into further detail, this variation in [27] was 0.73 for system 1 and 0.83 for system 2.

Figure 4: Simulation using NSGA-II and the Mathematical model: a) System 1 b) System 2

Figure 5: Simulation using NSGA-II and the ANN model: a) System 1 b) System 2

4.1.2. Simulation using the ANN model approach

The figures 5(a) and 5(b) show the systems' responses. The simulations of the NMPC strategy using the ANN model approach can be considered as more realistic. It can be seen that the controller performance is a bit poorer than the performance of the controller when the mathematical model is used, but the scenario of a partially unknown process is more likely to happen in the real world control context. The following section will show the results of the control system when the control strategy and the plant model are embedded in the real time controller and the Host real time target respectively, thus working on the HiL testing scenario.

4.2. Real Time simulation results on the HiL setup

In this experiment, the controller has been also implemented in Matlab[®]/Simulink[®], but adapting the code to run in RTAI by using C code. In this step the control strategy is embedded and executed on an Industrial PC, as described in section 3, while the systems to be controlled are running also in real time on a generic PC using the xPC Target real time OS. The results are shown in the same way as in the previous section. The table 2 shows the results for the HiL simulations.

4.2.1. Real time simulation using the mathematical model approach

The figures 6(a) and 6(b) show the systems' response. The results can be said to be good and very close to those obtained in the simulation stage.

		M_p_Max	M_p_Min	M_p_Mean	$M_p_Variance$	$Max \Delta u(k)$	e_{ss}
Math. Model	System 1	0.37	0.33	0.35	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.39	5%
	System 2	1.52	1.19	1.32	$6.641 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.40	3%
ANN Model	System 1	0.42	0.36	0.39	$2.16 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.36	7%
	System 2	1.65	1.46	1.46	$9.961 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.42	5%

Table 2: HiL using the mathematical and the ANN model approach

Figure 6: HiL using NSGA-II and the Mathematical model: a) System 1 b) System 2

4.2.2. Real time simulation using the ANN model approach

The figures 7(a) and 7(b) show the systems' response. The results show that the control strategy works correctly on industrial controllers, which proves that such hardware platforms can provide sufficient computational capabilities to execute this kind of complex control strategies.

4.3. Analysis of the computational cost

The tests performed in the previous sections do not show the full capabilities of the analysed controller hardware. The controller sampling time was not very high ($T_s = 0.2s$), and the NSGA-II was able to converge in this time. Therefore, another very interesting experiment of the control system performance involves the sample time reduction.

Figure 7: HiL using NSGA-II and the ANN model: a) System 1 b) System 2

In this experiment, the control sampling time has been progressively reduced in order to analyse the number of the iterations/generations that the NSGA-II is able to execute in that time.

The following table 3 has been obtained from 50 experiments for each sampling time and it shows the NSGA-II iterations/generation number vs. the control sampling time value.

	$T_s = 0.2s$	$T_s = 0.15s$	$T_s = 0.11s$	$T_s = 0.1s$	$T_s = 0.08s$	$T_s = 0.05s$	$T_s = 0.02$
Max. n^o It.	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Min. n^o It.	100	100	90	81	61	34	8
Mean. n^o It.	100	100	95.75	82.5	66.12	37.36	9.35
Mode. n^o It.	100	100	96	85	65	37	9
Variance	0	0	5.93	10.53	22.16	41.39	20.68
IAE 1 st objective	0.67	0.72	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.83	2.91
IAE 2 nd objective	0.098	0.098	0.098	0.099	0.103	0.124	0.647

Table 3: System 1, HiL Simulation + NSGA-II + ANN: GA iterations vs. sample time

According to these results, the worst case (min. Iteration n) starts to decay for a control sampling time of $T_s = 0.11s$. Anyhow, it must be remarked that the control itself is still good enough even when the number of iterations is cut by more than 60% ($T_s = 0.05s$), thus ensuring the robustness of the controller. This can be seen in the last two rows of the table 3 where the integral absolute error performance of the two objectives for each sample time is shown.

5. Conclusions

In this work a SC based iMO-NMPC strategy has been embedded and tested on a PC-Based industrial controller. In the control strategy, the NSGA-II multiobjective genetic algorithm is used as solver of the resulting multiobjective optimisation problem at each control sampling time in order to obtain the control action. The Nonlinear Model Predictive Control strategy needs a model approach of the plant to be controlled, thus mathematical models, as Artificial Neural Networks are, have been used, compared and tested. The entire strategy has been successfully implemented and executed in real time on the industrial controller.

The previous work presented in [27] showed the first implementations of this approach but lacks of the complexity of the multiobjective problem and, even more, it only used the mathematical model approach of the plant to be controlled. This last point is only applicable when the system to be controlled is completely or at least partially unknown. This means that the strategy has gained complexity since an ANN is used as an approach for the plant model. Furthermore, the considered Pareto based multiobjective optimisation context, in which two competing objectives for the control problem have been defined (these are not aggregated in a single cost function), together with the real time and deterministic execution requirements, increases even more the complexity of the implementation and testing task.

The work presents an exhaustive battery of testing results with the following combinations; (4.1.1) Numerical simulation + NSGA-II + math. model. (4.1.2) Numerical simulation + NSGA-II + ANN model. (4.2.1) HiL simulation + NSGA-II + math. model. (4.2.2) HiL simulation + NSGA-II + ANN model. These combinations represent a real workflow to implement SC based algorithms in real industrial platforms, from simulation to real time implementation. The obtained results show a good performance in each step, proving that the proposed multiobjective NMPC scheme works in different platforms and, what is even more important, that real industrial platforms are capable of running such complex control schemes within real time constraints.

A computational cost analysis of this control strategy running in the industrial controller (over the HiL simulation scenario) has been also presented in this paper, where the same control system has been tested considering more stringent time requirements. The objective of the analysis is to ascertain the accuracy of the controller under such stringent time restrictions, obtaining an empirical measure of the system performance degradation.

Future work will lead to optimising the code in order to achieve better performance of the controller from the point of view of the computational cost. It is also highly interesting to improve the decision making algorithm by adding expert rules as it was proposed in [26]. Another interesting research line will guide us to address complex multiple-input multiple-outputs (MIMO) control problems, with also multiple objectives, by using intelligent and hybrid control strategies.

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